

Quantum Frequency/Wavelength and the Normalization of Probability

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 22, 2024

In classical probability, $P(x)$ or $P(t)$ for static objects is defined on fixed length intervals. In classical physics, however, a probability seems to be assigned to moving objects (1) and is given by dt , the amount of time spent in a fixed length dx leading to $P(x) = C dt/v(x)$, where C is a normalization. The point we wish to make is that a fixed length is still needed for normalization (and a fixed T for $P(t)$). This fixed length appears naturally in a bound problem, but not for free particles. As a result, we suggest that there is an inherent issue with this probability due to normalization lengths and times. This does not mean, however, that one may simply eliminate the notion of $P(x)$ and $P(t)$.

We argue that for a free particle or photon, there is no fixed length or time interval physically, yet one should appear. If one considers a photon which must be in motion, then velocity = x/t and is associated with both space and time. At the same time, velocity = E/p . Given that p is linked explicitly with motion in space, one may suggest an inherent length constant/ p and an inherent time interval = constant/ E . Moreover, from Maxwell's equations, the speed of light in a vacuum is $1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ and does not change when viewed from a different frame. Thus: $E'/p' = x'/t' = c = E/p = x/t$. This leads to $-E't' + p'x' = -Et + px$, i.e. there is invariance in the problem.

For a particle with rest mass, there should also be an inherent length and mass. If the particle is at rest, there is no need for the concept of space, but time is still passing and so there should be a time interval. If one assumes that m_0 is proportional to a rest energy, then constant/ $m_0 b$, where b is some constant, should be the time interval. When the particle moves, there is now a full E and p . Given that p for a moving particle with rest mass imparts the same impact as a photon with the same p , we suggest that constant/ p must be the spatial length. This suggests then that constant/ E represents the time interval. Thus, we suggest that the idea of special relativity originates with the photon and carries over to a particle with rest mass. We try then to derive the Lorentz transformation using these ideas which start with the idea of a fixed length and time in space which is forced if one wishes to consider a probabilistic view point.

We further argue that if there is an intrinsic ruler and clock, there should be a ruler and clock generating function. Given that ruler and clock spacings are based on dynamic variables E, p , we suggest that these are frequency and wavelength in a kind of probability which defines a ruler or clock generating function. The continuity of this ruler or clock generating function may then be used to describe probabilistic motion not described by Newtonian mechanics such as one dimensional reflection-refraction.

Classical Probability

Classical probability suggests that one has $p_i \geq 0$ which sum to 1. Normalization is key in the definition of probability. If one has stationary objects in space and time and wishes to write $P(x)$ or $P(t)$, it seems that one must introduce a fixed length or time interval.

An issue arises if one tries to apply these probabilistic ideas to a moving object. In (1), it is suggested that one may use dt , the amount of time spent in a fixed dx , as being proportional to

probability. This idea is applied to a bound particle in which classically there is a fixed length between the classical turning points. So:

$$P(x) = C dx/v(x) \text{ where } v(x) \text{ is velocity ((1))}$$

What happens if one has a free particle with a constant velocity? In such a case, one would have to introduce various arbitrary lengths which are not physical.

Introduction of Intrinsic Lengths and Time Intervals

In a previous note, we discussed the idea of an intrinsic ruler and clock which a particle carries with it, namely, $\text{constant}/p$ and $\text{constant}/E$. We, however, did not give any particular reason why such a clock and ruler must exist. If one considers probability and insists on normalization, then it seems that for a free particle one cannot simply introduce artificial lengths and time intervals. We suggest that one requires a physical length and time in the problem.

In order to find this, we start with a photon. In such a case:

$$C = x/t = E/p \text{ or } -Et+px=0 \text{ ((2))}$$

From Maxwell's equations, $c=1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}$ which does not change when viewed from a constantly moving frame. Thus:

$$c = x'/t' = E'/p' \text{ assuming } x', t', E', p' \text{ differ when seen from a moving frame.}$$

$$\text{This leads to the idea of an invariant for a photon: } -Et+px = -E't'+p'x' \text{ ((3))}$$

We suggest that special relativity really follows from the considerations of a photon, because the notion of invariance follows from c being the same when viewed from different frames.

Given that one requires a fixed length and time interval, we suggest:

$$\text{constant}/E, \text{ constant}/p \text{ ((4))}$$

It is interesting to note that for a photon, p is defined by an impulse hit in space, not by velocity.

What about a particle with rest mass? In the rest frame, there is no need for the notion of space, but there is still time and if one wishes to introduce probability, one requires a time interval, i.e. $\text{constant}/\text{mob}$, where b is a constant.

If the particle with rest mass is viewed from a moving frame, there is a full E and p . Given that p is still an impulse, $\text{constant}/p$ should still represent a length. This suggests that $\text{constant}/E$ represents a time interval.

Now, ((3)) is of the form of a linear transformation, i.e.

$$-Et+px = \begin{pmatrix} E & t \\ A & B \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ t \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with } B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

For a photon, one cannot deduce A without examining Maxwell's equations, but for a particle with rest mass one can. We suggest that the same A applies for both. In such a case, $(0, m_0)$, where b is a constant, becomes (p, E) where p must be proportional to v and $-Et+px$ must be a constant i.e. $-m_0 b t$.

$$\text{Using } A = \begin{pmatrix} D & vN \\ vN & D \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{because B is used when creating a dot product} \quad ((6))$$

One has: $p = vN m_0$, $E = D m_0$ (acting on $(0, m_0)$) and $x' = vNt$, $t' = Dt$.

Now: $x'/t' = v = vN/D$ so $D=N$. Then:

$$E^2 - p^2 = -m_0^2 c^2 \quad \text{yields } N = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad \text{where b is a constant.} \quad ((7))$$

Given that these entire arguments follow from the photon having a c which is invariant with respect to frame motion, we choose $b=c$.

Thus, we argue that the probability leads to the notion of fixed lengths and time intervals which we argue cannot be arbitrary and from this one obtains the Lorentz transformation.

Further Implications

We next consider the case of a photon and one dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction junction). In such a case, one has c_1 and c_2 , not c for a vacuum, but the arguments of $-Et+px$ being a constant for the c_1 region and separately for the c_2 region still hold. In fact, $-Et+px=0$ does not depend on the value of c,

For one dimensional reflection-refraction, E is the same for incident, reflected and refracted photons, but p is different. If $-Et+px=0$, this suggests using $x=0$ for the n_1 - n_2 junction point and $t=0$ as well. One, however, cannot change the fact that the length unit is constant/ p_1 for $x<0$ and constant/ p_2 for $x>0$. Thus, not only are c and p discontinuous at $x=0$, but so is the length unit. If a length unit must exist for probabilistic reasons, then space should be created by a ruler made of such units. In other words, there is a periodic function in space with constant/p as its wavelength. This function should be a probability because these ideas all follow from probability. Furthermore, $P(x)dx=dx/L$, so this periodic probability should map to P(x) which represents a uniform distribution. These ideas lead to:

$$P_1(x) = \exp(ipx) \quad \text{unnormalized} \quad ((8))$$

One may finally suggest continuity of the ruler creating probability $P_1(x)$ because $\exp(-iEt)$ for time is continuous as well as E does not change. This suggests continuity of P_1 and its d/dx derivative, i.e.

$$A \exp(ip_1x) + B \exp(-ip_1x) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{at } x=0$$

$$Ap_1 \exp(ip_1x) - p_1 B \exp(-ip_1x) = Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((9b)) \quad \text{at } x=0$$

In other words, $\exp(ipx)$, is like a ruler generating function which creates the sense of length in space and it is this function (which at the same is like a probability which led to the notion of fixed length interval in the first place) which is continuous and determines how a photon (and also a particle with rest mass) behaves in space, instead of following Newtonian mechanics. The requirement that $P(x)dx = dx/L$ is the link with Newtonian mechanics.

Probability

We argued above that the ruler generating function, $\exp(ipx)$, is also a kind of probability because one must somehow resolve the length unit. Thus, it follows that the continuity of this ruler function (and its first derivative) may describe problems which involve probability in a natural way as may be seen for one dimensional reflection-refraction, i.e. $P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract}) = 1$ and one may arrive at the actual probability values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that to use probability to describe $P(x)$ or $P(t)$ for a classical particle, one needs the notion of a length or time interval for normalization. This is fine if there is a physical length or time interval as in the bound case, but is problematic for a free particle with constant p . We suggest that non-arbitrary length and time intervals are required and suggest that for a photon, the only variables available are E and p . P is measured by an impulse in space and so we use it to define an x interval, namely $\text{constant}/p$ and use $\text{constant}/E$ for the time interval. These follow from $x/t = E/p$. We also note that for a photon in a vacuum, different frames have the same c , so $-Et + px = 0 = -E't' + p'x'$. Thus, there is an invariant.

We extend these ideas to a particle with rest mass and argue that if $p=0$, there is no space, but still time and suggest that the time interval is $\text{constant}/\text{mob}$, where b is a constant. When viewed by a moving frame, one has E , p and we suggest that $\text{length} = \text{constant}/p$ and $\text{time interval} = \text{constant}/E$. We then deduce the form of the Lorentz transformation from these ideas noting that the notion of invariance followed from c being constant (vacuum value) when seen from different moving frames. Thus, the photon initiated the idea of special relativity in the discussion above.

Finally, we argue that if there are ruler lengths, there should be a ruler generating function, i.e. a kind of probability $P_1(x) = \exp(ipx)$. This function and its first derivative should be continuous and such a designation in space may actually be used to solve the behaviour of particles (including probabilistic behaviour) as we show by applying it to one dimensional photon reflection-refraction.

References

1. Majernick, V. and Optarny, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for the Quantum Oscillator

January 1999 Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General 29(9):2187
29(9):2187 DOI:[10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator